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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	Oxylin sMRM method		
Document creation date	09/08/2025	Principal investigator	Victoria Tyrrell
Institution	Cardiff University	Corresponding Email	tyrrellvj@cardiff.ac.uk
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	pH adjustment	Acetic acid pH3
2-phase system	2-step extraction	Special conditions	Hexane/IPA followed by Bligh and Dyer
Derivatization	N/A	Were internal standards used?	Yes
Deposition method	Pipetting	Internal standards used	2.1-2.9ng 12-HETE-d8, 15-HETE-d8, LTB4-d4 and PGE2-d4 standards (Cayman Chemical)

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Acetic acid	Number of separation dimensions	One dimension
Separation type 1	LC	Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP
Detector	Mass spectrometer	MS type	QTrap
MS vendor	SCIEX	Ion source	ESI
MS Level	MS ²	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution	Resolution at MS ²	Low
Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Profile mode	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank
Quality control	No		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Link to repository / ID to entry	10.17035/cardiff.30074749
Are metadata available?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification data
Raw data upload	Yes		

Sample Descriptions

BMDM macrophage supernatants / Mouse / Other liquid material

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze, Freeze-thaw cycles
Temperature handling original sample	Unknown	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	between 1 and 5 minutes	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Additives	None	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Additional preservation methods	No	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) Oxylipins[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Oxylipins	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Complete structure	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
319/219			
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	S/N>5 for quantitation	RT verified by standard	Yes
Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes	Model for separation prediction	No
Lipid Identification Software	None	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

1) Oxylipins[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Read data supplement	Read data supplement	Read data supplement	
Type of quantification	Calibration line	Type of calibration line	Solvent based
Species calibration line	Read Data supplement	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	S/N > 5
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Sciex OS
Batch correction	No		